

Structural aspects and physico-chemical properties of polysubstituted benzenes in benzene from relaxation phenomena

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Abstract : A brief report on the physico-chemical properties and structural aspects of some polysubstituted benzenes in benzene at different experimental temperatures under 10 GHz electric field is made to estimate relaxation times τ_j 's, dipole moments μ_j and thermodynamic energy parameters like enthalpy ΔH_τ , entropy ΔS_τ and free energy of activation ΔF_τ due to dielectric relaxation with formulations derived from orientational susceptibilities χ_{ij} 's, τ_j 's of the polar solutes obtained from the slope of the linear equation of χ'_{ij} and χ''_{ij} are, however, compared with those obtained from the ratio of the linear coefficients of individual variations of χ'_{ij} and χ''_{ij} with weight fractions w_j 's of the solute. τ_j 's from the later method are used to get thermodynamic energy parameters from the Eyring's rate process equation to shed more light on the physico-chemical properties of the polar liquid molecules concerned. The estimated μ_j 's in terms of linear coefficients β 's of $\chi'_{ij}-w_j$ equations and dimensionless parameters b 's involved with measured τ_j 's are finally compared with theoretical dipole moments μ_{theo} 's obtained from vector addition of available bond angles and bond moments of substituted polar groups. The estimated μ_{theo} gives valuable information regarding structures of the molecules. The slight disagreement between high frequency μ_j 's and μ_{theo} 's provides an interesting insight on the inductive, mesomeric and electromeric effects of the substituted polar groups attached to the parent molecules.

Keywords : Dipole moment, relaxation time, susceptibility.

Relaxation phenomena of polar liquid molecules in non-polar solvents under oscillating electric field in the GHz range at different experimental temperatures are of special importance as they are useful tools to investigate their physico-chemical properties as well as structural and associational aspects^{1,2}. The method is based on evaluation of relaxation time τ_j , dipole moment μ_j and thermodynamic energy parameters. There exists several methods^{3,4} to get τ_j 's and μ_j 's, but all these methods are not as simple as the present one in which a simultaneous determination of μ_j and τ_j is possible. Although several workers⁵⁻⁷ studied the relaxation mechanism of polar liquid molecules, but no such investigation on polysubstituted benzenes in terms of high frequency (hf) dielectric susceptibilities χ_{ij} 's has yet been made. The formulations derived so far may be used to study proteins, micelles, polymers and many other complex fluids⁸ including liquid crystals as well. Even binary mixtures of polar liquids can give rise to slow relaxation⁹. The formulations are concerned with the real χ'_{ij} ($= \epsilon'_{ij} - \epsilon_{\infty ij}$) and imaginary χ''_{ij} ($= \epsilon''_{ij}$) parts of hf complex dimensionless dielectric orientational susceptibility χ^*_{ij} .

The real ϵ'_{ij} and imaginary ϵ''_{ij} parts of high frequency permittivity ϵ^*_{ij} of polysubstituted benzenes like 1,3-diisopropyl benzene, *p*-methyl benzoyl chloride and *o*-chloroacetophenone in benzene at different weight fractions w_j 's of solutes in the temperature range of 30 to 45 °C under 10 GHz electric field were measured by Paul *et al.*¹⁰. The useful optical relative permittivities $\epsilon_{\infty ij}$'s to get concentration variation of χ'_{ij} were generated from Debye-Pallet's equations¹¹.

$$\epsilon'_{ij} = \epsilon_{\infty ij} + \frac{\epsilon_{0ij} - \epsilon_{\infty ij}}{1 + \omega^2 \tau_j^2} \quad (1)$$

and

$$\epsilon''_{ij} = \frac{\epsilon_{0ij} - \epsilon_{\infty ij}}{1 + \omega^2 \tau_j^2} \omega \tau_j \quad (2)$$

with the available τ_j 's previously determined by conductivity measurements¹². Paul *et al.*¹⁰ used the Gopalakrishna's method¹³ to measure τ_j 's from ϵ_{ij} 's in which all the polarisations including the fast polarisation

exist. If 1 is subtracted from low frequency ϵ_{0ij} and real ϵ'_{ij} , the corresponding static susceptibilities χ_{0ij} and real χ'_{ij} contain all the polarizations. When hf $\epsilon_{\infty ij}$ is subtracted from ϵ'_{ij} or static ϵ_{0ij} one obtains susceptibilities χ'_{ij} or χ_{0ij} respectively, involved with the orientational polarization alone to get accurate τ_j 's and μ_j 's.

Both the real ϵ'_{ij} and imaginary ϵ''_{ij} parts of ϵ^*_{ij} are related by¹⁴

$$\epsilon'_{ij} = \epsilon'_{\infty ij} + (1/\omega\tau_j) \epsilon''_{ij} \quad (3)$$

which in terms of established symbols of χ'_{ij} and χ''_{ij} becomes

$$\chi''_{ij} = \omega\tau_j \chi'_{ij} \quad (4)$$

Eq. (4) exhibit linear relationship between χ''_{ij} and χ'_{ij} as seen in Fig. 1. The slope $\omega\tau_j$ is used to get τ_j of a polar solute¹⁵. For most of the associative liquids studied elsewhere¹⁶, however, the variation of χ''_{ij} against χ'_{ij} is not strictly linear as seen in Figs. 2 and 3. Hence the slope of eq. (4) can be written as :

$$\frac{(d\chi''_{ij} / d\omega_j)_{\omega_j \rightarrow 0}}{(d\chi'_{ij} / d\omega_j)_{\omega_j \rightarrow 0}} = \omega\tau_j \quad (5)$$

containing τ_j 's of the present polar solutes. The τ_j 's estimated using eqs. (5) and (4) from both the methods are presented in Table 1. The excellent agreement between

Fig. 1. Variation of imaginary part χ''_{ij} against real part χ'_{ij} of the complex hf dielectric orientational susceptibility χ^*_{ij} of some polysubstituted benzenes in C_6H_6 under 10 GHz electric field at various experimental temperatures. *m*-Di-isopropylbenzene : Ia (\square) at 30°, Ib (\circ) at 35°, Ic (Δ) at 40°, Id (\times) at 45°; *p*-methylbenzylchloride : IIa (\square) at 30°, IIb (\circ) at 35°, IIc (Δ) at 40°, IIId (\times) at 45°; *o*-chloroacetophenone : IIIa (\square) at 30°, IIIb (\circ) at 35°, IIIc (Δ) at 40°, IIIId (\times) at 45°C.

Table 1. Estimated relaxation times τ_j 's, enthalpy ΔH_τ , entropy ΔS_τ and free energy ΔF_τ of activation due to dielectric relaxation, dimensionless parameter γ ($=\Delta H_\tau/\Delta H_{\eta j}$) from slope of $\ln \tau_j T$ vs $\ln \eta_j$ equation, enthalpy of activation $\Delta H_{\eta j}$ due to viscous flow of the solvent, estimated hf dipole moment μ_j and theoretical dipole moment μ_{theo} in coulomb metre (c.m.) of some polysubstituted benzenes in solvent C_6H_6 at different experimental temperatures in °C under 10 GHz electric field frequency

System with sl. no. and mol. wt. (kg)	Temp. (°C)	τ_j in psec (eq. 4)	τ_j in psec from eq. (5)	ΔH_τ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS_τ (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔF_τ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Value of δ	$\Delta H_{\eta j} = (\Delta H_{\tau/\eta})$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Estimated dipole moment $\mu \times 10^{30}$ c.m. with τ_j from eq. (5)	$\mu_{theo} \times 10^{30}$ c.m. from bond angles and reduced bond moments
(I) <i>m</i> -Di-isopropyl-benzene ($M_j = 0.162$)	30	8.80	8.80		109.01	10.12			12.70	
	35	7.33	7.33		108.09	9.86			13.87	
	40	5.46	5.46	43.15	108.16	9.30	6.96	6.20	13.99	3.77
	45	3.74	3.76		109.01	8.49			14.76	
(II) <i>p</i> -Methylbenzoyl chloride ($M_j = 0.156$)	30	2.72	2.72		-59.09	7.16			9.63	
	35	3.30	3.30		-60.26	7.82			9.82	
	40	3.23	3.23	-10.74	-59.66	7.93	-1.61	6.67	9.95	8.80
	45	3.24	3.24		-59.28	8.11			10.10	
(III) <i>o</i> -Chloroacetophenone ($M_j = 0.156$)	30	4.20	4.20		255.12	8.26			6.83	
	35	3.04	3.04		253.09	7.61			7.72	
	40	1.26	1.26	85.56	255.84	5.48	13.56	6.31	7.05	7.40
	45	0.90	0.90		254.21	4.72			6.48	

Fig. 2. Variation of imaginary part χ''_{ij} of hf susceptibility with weight fraction w_1 's of some polysubstituted benzenes in C_6H_6 under 10 GHz electric field at various experimental temperatures. *m*-Di-isopropylbenzene : Ia (\square) at 30°, Ib (O) at 35°, Ic (Δ) at 40°, Id (\times) at 45°; *p*-methylbenzylchloride : IIa (\square) at 30°, IIb (O) at 35°, IIc (Δ) at 40°, IID (\times) at 45°; *o*-chloroacetophenone : IIIa (\square) at 30°, IIIb (O) at 35°, IIIc (Δ) at 40°, IIId (\times) at 45°C.

Fig. 3. Variation of imaginary part χ''_{ij} of hf susceptibility with weight fraction w_1 's of some polysubstituted benzenes in C_6H_6 under 10 GHz electric field at various experimental temperatures. *m*-Di-isopropylbenzene : Ia (\diamond) at 30°, Ib (\square) at 35°, Ic (Δ) at 40°, Id (\times) at 45°; *p*-methylbenzylchloride : IIa (\diamond) at 30°, IIb (\square) at 35°, IIc (Δ) at 40°, IID (\times) at 45°; *o*-chloroacetophenone : IIIa (\diamond) at 30°, IIIb (\square) at 35°, IIIc (Δ) at 40°, IIId (\times) at 45°C.

τ_j 's indicates that the polar-polar interactions are almost eliminated in the limit of $w_j = 0$ to give reliable τ_j by the latter method¹⁷. The correlation coefficients r 's and relative errors of both the plots in Figs. 2 and 3 were obtained by regression analysis. They are within the range of 0.93 to 0.99 and 0.0008 to 0.0001 respectively, hereby indicating how far both χ''_{ij} 's and χ'_{ij} 's are correlated with w_j 's. It is evident from Table 1 that τ_j 's decrease with temperature. At constant temperature τ_j depends on the energy difference between the activated and normal states. At higher temperatures thermal agitation causes an increase in energy loss due to larger number of collisions and thereby decreases the values of τ_j 's. For *m*-diisopropyl benzenes the τ_j 's are greater in comparison to *p*-methyl benzoyl chloride and *o*-chloro acetophenone probably due to bigger size of the molecules containing higher number of carbon atoms. For systems II and III τ_j 's do not vary much with temperature because of the presence of the same number of C-atoms in both the molecules. *p*-Methyl benzoyl chloride shows reverse variation of τ_j with temperature. Inductive effect of CH_3 group put the $C=O$ group of $COCl$ to exist as dipolar structure

($>C^+-O^-$), therefore increase in temperature has no significant effect on τ_j of this system.

Dielectric relaxation is a process of rotation of polar molecule under hf electric field and it requires an activation energy ΔF_τ to overcome the potential energy barrier between two equilibrium positions. ΔF_τ is related to estimated τ_j by¹⁹

$$\tau_j = (A/T) e^{\Delta F_\tau / RT} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{where } \Delta F_\tau = \Delta H_\tau - T\Delta S_\tau \quad (7)$$

From eqs. (6) and (7) it follows that

$$\ln \tau_j T = \ln A' + (\Delta H_\tau / R) 1/T \quad (8)$$

$$\text{where } A' = A e^{-\Delta S_\tau / R}$$

Eq. (8) is a straight line when $\ln(\tau_j T)$ is plotted against $1/T$ as seen in Fig. 4, the slope and intercept are used to get enthalpy of activation ΔH_τ , entropy of activation ΔS_τ and free energy of activation ΔF_τ due to dielectric relaxation as presented in Table 1. The enthalpy of activation ΔH_τ

Fig. 4. The linear plot of $\ln(\tau_j T)$ against $1/T$ of some polystybenzenes in C_6H_6 under 10 GHz electric field. (I) *m*-Diisopropylbenzene (Δ) using τ_j of eq. (2), (II) *p*-methylbenzylchloride (\times) using τ_j of eq. (2), (III) *o*-chloroacetophenone (O) using τ_j of eq. (2).

due to viscous flow of the solvent is ascertained from the slope δ ($= \Delta H_\tau / \Delta H_{\eta_i}$) of the linear equation of $\ln \tau_j T$ against $\ln \eta_i$, where η_i is the coefficient of viscosity of the solvent used.

It is evident from Table 1 and Fig. 4 that for system II the linear eq. (8) has negative slope to give negative ΔH_τ because for that system τ_j 's increases with temperature. The systems I and III shows positive ΔS_τ 's which suggest that the configuration involved in dipolar rotation has an activated state which is less ordered than the normal state²⁰. Unlike *p*-methyl benzoyl chloride both systems I and III show $\delta > 0.50$ (as seen in Table 1) indicating solvent environment around solute molecules to behave as solid phase rotators^{18,20}. ΔH_{η_i} in Table 1 involved with translational and rotational motions of the molecule is of lower value than those of ΔH_τ 's in which only the rotational motion occurs. The Debye factors $\tau_j T / \eta_i$ unlike Kalman factors $\tau_j T / \eta_i^\gamma$ at all temperatures are of constant orders for each system. This at once reflects the validity of Debye model¹⁸ of dielectric relaxation for such compounds in benzenes under 10 GHz electric field.

Theoretical formulations :

In order to obtain hf dipole moment μ_j , the Debye-Smyth's relation^{21,22} in terms of hf χ''_{ij} 's is used

$$\chi''_{ij} = \frac{N\rho_{ij}\mu_j^2}{27\epsilon_0 M_j k_B T} \left(\frac{\omega\tau_j}{1 + \omega^2\tau_j^2} \right) (\epsilon_{ij} + 2)^2 w_j \quad (9)$$

where M_j = molecular weight of the solute in kg.

ϵ_{ij} = relative permittivity of solution (ij)

ρ_{ij} = density of solution (ij)

k_B = Boltzmann constant

Eq. (9) on differentiation with respect to w_j and at $w_j \rightarrow 0$

$$\left(\frac{d\chi''_{ij}}{dw_j} \right)_{w_j \rightarrow 0} = \frac{N\rho_{ij}\mu_j^2}{27\epsilon_0 M_j k_B T} \left(\frac{\omega\tau_j}{1 + \omega^2\tau_j^2} \right) (\epsilon_j + 2)^2 \quad (10)$$

in the limit $w_j = 0$, because $\rho_{ij} \rightarrow \rho_i$, $\epsilon_{ij} \rightarrow \epsilon_i$ are the density, relative permittivity of solvent benzene. From eqs. (5) and (10) one obtains

$$\mu_j = \left[\frac{27\epsilon_0 M_j k_B T \beta}{N\rho_i (\epsilon_i + 2)^2 b} \right]^{1/2} \quad (11)$$

where $b = 1/(1 + \omega^2\tau_j^2)$ is a dimensionless parameter associated with estimated τ_j of eq. (5), β is the linear coefficient of χ'_{ij-w_j} curves of Fig. 3.

Experimental

The microwave radiations of frequency 10 GHz, generated by a Gunn oscillator fed by 10 volt dc power supply were passed through the isolator, tuner, frequency meter, attenuator and a slotted line fitted with a probe connected with a crystal detector and a VSWR meter. The other end of the slotted line was connected to a 6.4 cm long silvered waveguide cell which was connected to a thermostat by a 90° bend to carry out the experimental values of ϵ'_{ij} and ϵ''_{ij} at different temperatures¹⁰.

The viscosity η_i and density ρ_i of benzene at various experimental temperatures were measured using an Ubbelohde viscometer and a pycnometer respectively. The analytical grade polystybenzenes like 1,3-diisopropyl benzene, *p*-methyl benzoyl chloride and *o*-chloroacetophenone as well as the solvent benzene were supplied by Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. They were further purified by repeated fractional distillations and the physical constants like density, viscosity and relative permittivity ϵ_i of solvent C_6H_6 were checked in agreement with the literature values¹⁰. The polar liquids were kept over molecular sieve of mesh 4 Å for 48

h with occasional shaking. They were then distilled through a long vertical fractionating column and the middle fractions were used for the present study. Benzene (B.D.H., Analar) was purified by refluxing over sodium metal for 6 h and then distilled through a long vertical fractionating column. The middle fraction of the solvent was used to make solutions of different w_j 's of the respective solutes at different experimental temperatures²⁶.

Results and discussion

The μ_j 's thus measured at all temperatures are entered in Table 1. Almost all the $\chi'_{ij}-w_j$ curves have a tendency to come closer within the range $0.00 < w_j < 0.03$ probably due to almost same polarity of the molecules²² arising out of solute-solvent or solute-solute molecular association which may be supposed to be physico-chemical properties¹⁴ of the systems. This can be inferred from the nonlinear variation of μ_j-t curves of Fig. 5. Unlike the system I and II, *o*-chloroacetophenone (system III) shows minimum μ_j 's at lower and higher temperatures. In the vicinity of $-\text{COCH}_3$ and Cl, the electronic factor may operate between the carbonyl oxygen and Cl atom at *ortho* position may be the reason for its anomalous behaviour towards μ_j value as seen in Fig. 6. The minimum μ_j 's indicate the attainment of slight symmetry in the molecules at those temperatures¹⁸. The monotonic increase of μ_j with temperature for *p*-methyl benzoyl chloride oc-

Fig. 5. Plot of measured dipole moment μ_j in Coulomb metre [using τ_j by our method i.e. eq. (5)] with temperatures t in $^{\circ}\text{C}$ of some polysubstituted benzenes in C_6H_6 under 10 GHz electric field. (I) *m*-Di-isopropylbenzene (\square) using τ_j of eq. (2), (II) *p*-methylbenzylchloride (Δ) using τ_j of eq. (2), (III) *o*-chloroacetophenone (O) using τ_j of eq. (2).

Fig. 6. Conformational structures of different polysubstituted benzenes with dipole moment $\mu_{\text{theo}} \times 10^{30}$ in Coulomb metre (c.m.). (I) *m*-Di-isopropylbenzene, (II) *p*-methylbenzylchloride, (III) *o*-chloroacetophenone.

cur for its increasing molecular asymmetry at higher temperatures. The above nature of μ_j-t curves arises due to alignment of different types of bondings among the solute and solvent molecules which are either formed or broken to some extent^{23,24}. Thus the measured μ_j 's reflects the stability or instability of the molecules. This is confirmed by different thermodynamic energy parameters in order to make a strong comment on their physico-chemical properties.

Theoretical dipole moment's μ_{theo} 's, as seen in Fig. 6. are, however, considered by vector addition of bond moments of substituted polar groups of molecules from the available infrared spectroscopic data of bond moments assuming the molecules to be planar ones. They are placed in Table 1 to compare them with the measured hf μ_j 's. The molecules under study have polar groups and there is large probability of intramolecular group rotations and, therefore, these molecules may not be represented by simple Debye type dielectric dispersions. On the otherhand, Higasi's equation⁷ for single frequency in dilute solutions or Higasi's frequency variation method could, however, be used to evaluate those group rotations for such molecules. But the molecules are very simple and the purpose of the paper is to see the applicability of Debye type dispersions in them in evaluating τ_j and μ_j which are claimed to be accurate with 10% and 5% respectively. The molecules of polysubstituted benzenes

referred to tables and figures are planar and have the property of cyclic delocalization of π electrons on each C-atom. The solvent benzene is a cyclic and planar compound with three double bonds and six p -electrons on six carbon atoms of the benzene ring. Hence π - π interaction or resonance effect combined with an inductive effect commonly known as mesomeric effect in excited state called the electromeric effect is expected to play the prominent role in μ_j 's. The slight disagreement between hf μ_j 's and μ_{theo} 's of Fig. 6 is explained on the basis of the fact that the flexible polar groups of the molecules are greatly influenced by hf electric field to yield the inductive, mesomeric and electromeric effects in them to give higher μ_j values, especially for *m*-diisopropyl benzene. All these effects, are, however, incorporated in their structures by multiplying the bond moments by a factor μ_j/μ_{theo} to make μ_{theo} 's closer to μ_j 's as sketched in Fig. 6. The electromeric effect caused by $>C=O$ in the 2nd and 3rd molecules may be the reason to make μ_j 's more closer to μ_{theo} 's²⁵.

Conclusion :

The theoretical formulations in terms of internationally accepted and established symbols of established dielectric terminologies and parameters in SI units are more topical, significant and simpler one to have deep insight into the physico-chemical, structural and associational aspects of polysubstituted benzenes in C_6H_6 at different temperatures under 10 GHz electric field. The conformational structures so far sketched in Fig. 6 are also significant because they enhance the scientific content of the existing knowledge of dielectric relaxation processes. The curves satisfied by experimental points in all the figures reflect the validity of the theoretical formulations based on Debye model to estimate several physical parameters such as τ_j 's, μ_j 's and ΔH_τ , ΔF_τ , ΔS_τ etc. which are more of archival values to study the temperature variation of physico-chemical properties of dipolar molecules. The uncertainty in the evaluated τ_j and μ_j values are of 10% and 5% errors which are claimed to be accurate.

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